

**REPUBLIC OF HAITI
MINISTERE DES AFFAIRES ETRANGERES
SECRETARIAT TECHNIQUE DE LA COMMISSION MIXTE
HAITIANO – DOMINICAINE**

**PELIGRE – DOS BOCAS BI-NATIONAL PROJECT
RECOMMENDATIONS TO THE DOS BOCAS PROJECT**

**Prepared by
Francis Mitchell M.S., P.E.
President Soleo Energies Inc.**

July 2023

Francis Mitchell, M.S., P.E.
8365 SW 112th Street
Miami, Florida 33156

Le 7 Juillet 2023

Référence : Évaluation du projet binational de Dos Bocas

Monsieur le Ministre,

J'ai l'avantage de vous faire parvenir, sous couvert de la présente, un rapport intitulé « *Projet binational de Péligre et de Dos Bocas – Recommandations au Projet Dos Bocas* » préparé bénévolement suite à des discussions avec le Consul Honoraire du Royaume de Norvège en Haïti Monsieur Philippe Bayard et l'Ambassadeur Pierre Karly Jean Jeune, Secrétaire Technique de la Partie haïtienne de la Commission Mixte Haïtiano-Dominicaine, à partir de la documentation existante.

En effet, suite aux nombreux échanges avec mes deux amis, haïtiens comme moi, j'ai élaboré ce rapport pour deux raisons, à savoir : aider à la prévention de l'impact négatif de la perte du barrage hydro-électrique de Péligre sur l'économie nationale d'une part et contribuer à la concrétisation de l'idée de projet binational de Dos Bocas, vieille de près de quarante ans, d'autre part.

Comme vous le remarquerez à la lecture dudit rapport, ce travail d'évaluation doit être perçu comme une contribution patriotique, Dos Bocas étant un projet très important avec de grands avantages pour la République d'Haïti : création d'un vaste réservoir pour réguler le débit du Fleuve Artibonite, laminage des crues et protection contre les inondations en aval, garantie à Péligre d'un débit minimum de 41 m³/s nécessaire à l'irrigation de la vallée de l'Artibonite et enfin production d'une quantité considérable d'énergie.

Dans la littérature disponible en République Dominicaine, il n'a pas été pris en considération les contraintes d'élévation du site de Dos Bocas et les exigences minimales d'exploitation pouvant affecter le fonctionnement de Péligre. Dans mon rapport, je propose une alternative audit site et définis également les procédures d'exploitation minimales pour une opération en cascade avec la centrale de Péligre. L'opération en cascade augmentera la production d'énergie de Péligre à un niveau proche de celui de l'année 1972, tout en maintenant un débit minimum de 41 m³/s pour l'irrigation pendant la saison sèche. D'autres éléments de discussion utiles pour la République d'Haïti et la République Dominicaine y sont aussi énoncés.

Comme mentionné plus haut, j'ai réalisé l'étude de manière bénévole, ayant constaté l'urgence de l'état critique du barrage hydro-électrique de Péligre. J'ai coordonné

les détails avec l'Ambassadeur Jean Jeune, un très bon ami à moi depuis le collège. Mon seul souhait est que les recommandations formulées fassent avancer le projet vers sa mise en œuvre au bénéfice du développement du pays.

Tout en restant disponible pour des échanges avec vous et d'autres autorités concernées par cette problématique, je vous prie de croire, Monsieur le Ministre, en ma franche collaboration.

Francis **Mitchell, M.S., P.E.**

**SON EXCELLENCE MONSIEUR JEAN VICTORE GÉNÉUS
MINISTRE
MINISTÈRE DES AFFAIRES ÉTRANGÈRES ET DES CULTES
5, Musseau, Pétion-Ville**

EN SES BUREAUX.

CC : Consul Honoraire Philippe Bayard

Ambassadeur Pierre Karly Jean Jeune

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this report is to offer an alternate location for the Dos Bocas hydroelectric project as proposed by the Dominican Republic, and sets the operating parameters for any hydroelectric project planned within the Artibonite Watershed upstream of Peligre. The previous study did not consider the effect of Dos Bocas to the operation of Peligre. In order to set these operational parameters, the Peligre reservoir and hydroelectric facility had to be evaluated to establish a minimum baseline. This report has evaluated these parameters and is proposing an alternate location for Dos Bocas that will greatly benefit Peligre, and increase the energy production for either Dos Bocas and Peligre. To complete this study and formulate the operational recommendations, a new "Reservoir Rule Curve" has been modelled. In total more than 75 operational simulations of Peligre and Dos Bocas operating in cascade have been performed. This report and back up documentations support the findings of this study.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	1
2	Peligre Hydropower Facility	2
2.1	Description	2
2.2	Peligre “Reservoir Rule Curve”	2
2.3	Peligre Reservoir Sedimentation History	4
2.4	Peligre Generating Capacity Baseline	7
3	Dos Bocas Hydropower Facility	10
3.1	Dos Bocas Project Proposal by INDRHI.....	10
3.2	Peligre and Dos Bocas Average Monthly Flow	10
3.3	Peligre and Dos Bocas Operational Calibration and Simulation	11
4	Conclusion.....	16
5	References	17
	Appendix A Peligre Capacity Baseline Evaluation	18
	Appendix B Dos Bocas Capacity Optimization – Results of Simulation.....	23
	Appendix C Peligre and Dos Bocas Cascade Operation	26
	Appendix D Peligre and Dos Bocas Exhibits.....	29

List of Figures

Figure 1:	Peligre Current Reservoir Rule Curve	3
Figure 2:	Peligre Reservoir Historical variation of Lake Surface Area and Storage	5
Figure 3:	Peligre Reservoir Historical Sediment Deposition Profile	6
Figure 4:	Peligre Proposed "Reservoir Rule Curve"	8
Figure 5:	Dos Bocas Optimum Design Flow Effect on "Dos Bocas + Peligre" Capacity ...	13
Figure 6:	Dos Bocas Optimum Minimum Flow Effect on "Dos Bocas + Peligre" Capacity	14

List of Tables

Table 1: Peligre General Data	2
Table 2: Peligre Reservoir Historical Variation of Surface Area and Volume	4
Table 3: Artibonite River Monthly Flow Variation at Peligre.....	7
Table 4: Peligre Baseline Energy Production Simulation for Selected Reservoir	9
Table 5: Dos Bocas Project Data Proposal by INDRHI	10
Table 6: Peligre and Dos Bocas Average Monthly Flow by Water Balance	11
Table 7: Dos Bocas Project Data Alternate Proposal	11
Table 8: Peligre and Dos Bocas General Results	12
Table 9: Peligre and Dos Bocas Average Monthly Power Capacity Working in Cascade	15

1 Introduction

The Artibonite River is the longest river in the island of Quisqueya with a length of 321 km. Its watershed drains the central plateau of Quisqueya and has an area of 9,500 km² of which 6,800 Km² are in Haiti, and 2,700 km² are in the Dominican Republic. In 1956 the Peligre dam was constructed in Haiti with the purpose of regulating the flow of the river for irrigation and flood protection. The implementation of this structure and reservoir provided the needed water to irrigate 17,000 hectares of very fertile lands.

In 1972 the second phase of the construction was completed with the installation of three hydraulic turbines of the Francis type with a combined capacity of 54 Mw. Economically the Peligre dam is a valuable asset for Haiti having an impact on both the agriculture, and the energy needs of the country.

Over the years the natural process of sedimentation of the reservoir has accelerate to the point that the useful life of the reservoir is being affected. The useful life originally had been estimated at 180 years to end in 2137. Various studies to estimate the remaining useful life of Peligre has been performed, and proposals have also been made to extend its useful life. One such proposal is to construct a dam upstream of Peligre's reservoir at the confluence of the Artibonite River with the Macassia River, right at the Haitian-Dominican border. This proposal was elaborated in 1985 by the "Instituto Nacional de Recursos Hidraulicos" (INDRHI) of the Dominican Republic. This project is widely referred to as "Dos Bocas".

A concept paper for Dos Bocas has been prepared by INDRHI for a 90 Mw hydroelectric facility that will be jointly operated by the Republic of Haiti, and the Dominican Republic. The alternate goal for this project is to also create a sediment capture reservoir that will benefit Peligre. However, the modeling simulation of having the Peligre and Dos Bocas reservoir operating in cascade has not yet been evaluated. This report will establish the baseline operating criteria for Peligre prior to Dos Bocas, propose a new conceptual approach for Dos Bocas, and finally presents the operating "reservoir rule curve" for Peligre and Dos Bocas working in cascade.

2 Peligre Hydropower Facility

2.1 Description

The Peligre dam is of the buttress type with a height of 70 m, and a length of 263 m. The crest of the dam is set at elevation 175.50 m creating a large reservoir of 39.76 km² at normal pool elevation of 172.00 m. The critical elevations and generating capacity for Peligre is shown in table 1.

Items	
Watershed area	6,700 km ²
Dam crest elevation	175.50 m
Maximum water elevation	173.60 m
Full reservoir elevation	172.00 m
Spillway elevation	167.00 m
Lowest water elevation	153.00 m
Turbine intake elevation	130.60 m
Turbine center elevation	118.00 m
Tail water elevation	118.60 m
Turbine force main diameter	3.80 m
Turbine type	Francis
Amount of turbine	3
Turbine design flow	41.00 m ³ /s
Turbine power	18 Mw
Total installed power	54 Mw

Table 1: Peligre General Data

2.2 Peligre “Reservoir Rule Curve”

The Peligre dam was constructed to regulate the flow of the Artibonite River to supply water for irrigation during the dry season, and to provide flood protection during the rainy season. Per design the minimum flow release had been set at 45.00 m³/s. However, this minimum flow has been adjusted to 41.00 m³/s which is the design flow of a single working turbine. The “Reservoir Rule Curve” that is currently implemented specifies the minimum reservoir stage during the dry season to satisfy the minimum flow release, and the maximum reservoir stage during the rainy season for flood control protection. This “Reservoir Rule Curve” has not been designed to maximize the production of electrical energy, and is the root cause of the upstream sediments being channelize toward the dam. This curve needs to be re-evaluated by considering both minimum flow release, and optimum energy production. The sedimentation of the reservoir has affected its volume to such an extent that the current curve is no longer valid. Figure 1 illustrates Peligre current “Reservoir Rule Curve”.

Figure 1: Peligre Current Reservoir Rule Curve

2.3 Peligre Reservoir Sedimentation History

At its inauguration in 1956, Peligre reservoir covered an area of 39.76 km² at normal pool elevation of 172 m, and the total storage was evaluated at 599 Mm³. In 1979 a bathymetric survey of the reservoir was performed and although the surface area barely changed (39.81 km²), the total storage decreased to 470 Mm³. The sediment line through the center of the reservoir has been surveyed in 1956, 1979, 1980, and 2008.

In 2016 a Lidar survey of the country has been made available which covers portion of the reservoir above normal pool. This report used the Lidar data to set the sediment line, and to extrapolate that line below normal pool. From the 2016 Lidar and extrapolated values, the reservoir at normal pool elevation of 172 m covers an area of 31.47 km², and the storage volume at 262 Mm³. Table 2 below shows the reservoir area and volume at various elevations. This table shows that in 60 years of operations the volume of the reservoir has decreased by 56%. The variations of the reservoir area and volume are illustrated in figure 2, and the variations of the sediment line from dam to beginning of reservoir are illustrated in figure 3.

ELEVATION (m)	AREA (km²) (1956)	AREA (km²) (1979)	AREA (km²) (2016)	CUMULATIVE VOLUME (Mm³) (1956)	CUMULATIVE VOLUME (Mm³) (1979)	CUMULATIVE VOLUME (Mm³) (2016)
132.00	0.99	0.43	0.03	4.85	0.47	0.00
135.00	2.10	1.55	0.17	11.62	5.17	0.20
140.00	4.54	3.76	2.32	26.60	20.68	2.27
145.00	7.61	5.50	3.75	52.95	42.81	15.38
150.00	11.33	7.04	5.23	97.13	71.75	35.09
153.00	13.93	8.31	6.07	134.34	94.00	51.74
155.00	15.85	9.48	6.50	164.16	111.80	64.13
160.00	21.35	14.24	7.65	257.60	171.28	97.79
165.00	28.06	22.43	10.33	379.55	262.62	137.17
166.00	29.56	24.52	11.67	407.45	286.09	147.60
167.00	31.11	26.76	12.68	436.51	311.63	159.46
168.00	32.73	29.13	13.52	466.74	339.40	172.33
169.00	34.40	31.64	21.29	498.13	369.56	186.19
170.00	36.13	34.27	24.76	530.67	402.29	208.16
171.00	37.91	37.00	27.01	564.35	437.76	233.82
172.00	39.76	39.81	31.48	599.16	476.16	262.32
173.00	41.66	42.69	36.00	635.07	517.68	296.35
173.60	42.83	44.43	37.90	657.15	544.16	319.19
175.00	45.64	48.52	41.48	710.16	610.85	378.40
175.55	46.77	50.12	42.60	731.55	639.01	404.38

Table 2: Peligre Reservoir Historical Variation of Surface Area and Volume

Figure 2: Peligre Reservoir Historical variation of Lake Surface Area and Storage

Figure 3: Peligre Reservoir Historical Sediment Deposition Profile

2.4 Peligre Generating Capacity Baseline

Since 1972, at the inauguration of Peligre, the Electricity of Haiti (EDH) has faced many hurdles in the operation of the hydroelectric facility. Soon after inauguration, one of the turbines became inoperative, and the high-tension line linking Peligre to Port-au-Prince could not handle the full production capacity from the turbines. In 2018 Peligre underwent a major electrical and mechanical rehabilitation of its turbines.

In 1972 the annual energy production was 320 Gwh which translates into a yearly average power of 37 Mw, a maximum power of 47 Mw during the rainy season, and a minimum power of 22 Mw during the dry season. In 2008 the annual energy production was 150 Gwh for a yearly average power of 17 Mw, a maximum power 30 Mw during the rainy season, and a minimum power of 10 Mw during the dry season.

In order to establish a baseline of the energy production capability of Peligre, various numerical simulations of the production have been performed using reservoir storage data from 1956, 1979, and 2016. The river flow data used in these simulations is an average of flow measurement records taken since 1932 for a period of 45 years. Table 3 lists the monthly average flow of the Artibonite River at Peligre.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
	m ³ /s											
Max.	40	56	46	96	376	330	245	167	235	282	232	119
Avg.	24	22	20	33	130	153	98	94	133	154	83	44
Min.	3	4	4	3	47	48	45	37	53	52	29	11

Table 3: Artibonite River Monthly Flow Variation at Peligre

The baseline simulations have been carried for the 1956, 1979, and 2016 reservoir storage but with the following constraints.

1. Minimum flow release of 41 m³/s.
2. Maximum reservoir elevation of 172.00 m.
3. Minimum reservoir elevation of 153.00 m.
4. Utilize the Artibonite River average monthly flow hydrograph.

A new "Reservoir Rule Curve" is being proposed as shown in figure 4. The current one is no longer applicable due to the reduction of the flood control storage volume. For flood control a new overflow weir set at elevation 173.00 m will need to be constructed. This option has been proposed in 1998 by the firm of COB-LGL and published in a feasibility study titled "Etude de surelevation du barrage de Peligre – Rapport de faisabilité". Implementation of the new "Reservoir Rule Curve" will require rainfall monitoring, and real time river gauging monitoring of streams located within the watershed.

TURBINE			PRIMARY TURBINE			SECONDARY TURBINE			TERTIARY TURBINE		
SETTING			RIVER FLOW CONDITION			EXCESS FLOW CONDITION			EXCESS FLOW CONDITION		
			(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(1)	(2)	(3)
	TURBINE STATUS	TURBINE FLOW TYPE	$Q_{inf} \leq Q_r$	$Q_r < Q_{inf} < Q_f$	$Q_{inf} \geq Q_f$	$Q \leq Q_r$	$Q_r < Q < Q_f$	$Q \geq Q_f$	$Q \leq Q_r$	$Q_r < Q < Q_f$	$Q \geq Q_f$
Maximum Water Surface El.	On	Qf	Qr	Qinf	Qf	0	Q	Qf	0	Q	Qf
Top Flood Control Zone El.				Qo			Q			Q	
Top Conservation Zone El.		Qinf * F		O * F			O * F				
Top Inactive Zone El.		Qr		Qr	Qr		Qr	Qr			
	Off	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Qf	Turbine Full Flow (Maximum Power Output)									
	Qr	Turbine Reduced Flow (Minimum Power Output) or River Minimum Residual									
	Qo	Turbine Optimum Flow (Maximum Efficiency)									
	Q	Excess River									
	Qinf	River Flow									
	F	Flow Reduction Factor									
		Surcharge Zone - Maximum Power Output & Turbines set at Maximum Flow									
		Flood Control Zone - Maximum Power Output & Turbines set at Maximum Efficiency Flow									
		Conservation Zone - Minimum Power Output & Turbines set at Minimum Flow									
		Inactive Zone - All Turbines Off									
	(1)	River Flow or Excess River Flow less than or equal than Turbine Minimum Flow									
	(2)	River Flow or Excess River Flow more than Turbine Minimum Flow but less than Turbine Maximum									
	(3)	River Flow or Excess River Flow more than or equal than Turbine Maximum Flow									

Figure 4: Peligre Proposed "Reservoir Rule Curve"

As the sedimentation of the reservoir is progressing, the minimum flow release will not be compatible with the operation of the facility for energy production. A simulation will also be performed to show what will be the minimum flow release necessary to maximize energy production. The results of these simulations are listed in table 4, and the detailed outputs shown in Appendix A.

Simulation	Energy (Gwh)	Average Power (Mw)	Minimum Flow (m³/s)	Minimum Elevation (m)	Remark
1956 Storage	284.37	32.46	41	167.00	Min. Flow Control
1979 Storage	284.87	32.52	41	167.00	Min. Flow Control
2016 Storage	279.96	31.96	41	161.00	Min. Flow Control
2016 Storage	284.38	32.46	21	172.00	Max. Energy Control

Table 4: Peligre Baseline Energy Production Simulation for Selected Reservoir

The results of table 4 demonstrates that with an updated “Reservoir Rule Curve”, it is possible to maximize the energy production and maintain a higher minimum reservoir elevation. A higher reservoir elevation during the dry season is recommended in order to prevent the migration of upstream deposited sediments to the downstream area of the reservoir. Keeping the reservoir level at its highest will guarantee a higher energy production but at the detriment of the minimum flow release needed for the agriculture. Eventually this will be a choice that the country will need to consider because at the end the full sedimentation of the reservoir will spell the end of either energy production or the minimum flow release.

Any large hydroelectric project upstream of the Peligre reservoir will need to be designed in such a way for not adversely impact the operation of Peligre. At a minimum the following operational requirements at Peligre running in cascade with an upstream hydroelectric facility should be:

1. Maintain a minimum discharge of 41.00 m³/s.
2. Decrease reservoir level fluctuation to 1979 level, or near elevation 172.00 m.
3. Provide flood relief to cover Peligre reservoir loss of storage.
4. Construct new overflow weir to handle millennium flood.
5. Increase energy production to near 1979 production.

These five recommendations will form the basis of the Republic of Haiti’s proposal to the Dominican Republic’s for the Dos Bocas Project.

3 Dos Bocas Hydropower Facility

3.1 Dos Bocas Project Proposal by INDRHI

The Dos Bocas project as proposed will be set at the confluence of the Artibonite River with The Macassia River. At project setting the tributary watershed covers an area of 5,896 km². The project data as per INDRHI proposal are listed in table 5.

ITEMS		
Dam Crest	235.00	m
Maximum Water Level	232.50	m
Minimum Water Level	208.00	m
Power House	170.00	m
Gross Head	62.50	m
Maximum Flow	200.00	m ³ /s
Minimum Flow	57.20	m ³ /s
Design Flow	200.00	m ³ /s
Maximum Power	90.00	Mw
Minimum Power	23.00	Mw
Average Power	23.52	Mw
Annual Energy Output	206,000,000	Mwh
Reservoir Area	84.71	km ²
Reservoir Volume	1.38	km ³

Table 5: *Dos Bocas Project Data Proposal by INDRHI*

This proposal as per the study is for the construction of two dams, and two reservoirs linked by a channel. One dam will be on the Artibonite River just downstream of the Guayamouc River, and the other dam will be on the Macassia River. The two reservoirs will be linked by a channel to equilibrate the water levels. However, this proposal was based on 20 meters contour maps instead of the Lidar data. The following items need to be considered:

1. Dam crest elevation of 235.00 m is higher than 226.00 m which is the elevation of the city of Hinche.
2. Power house elevation of 170.00 m is lower than 175.50 m which is Peligre dam crest elevation.
3. Maximum and minimum flows are higher than Peligre historical flow.
4. No operational simulation of Dos Bocas with Peligre.

This study will propose an alternative to the INDRHI concept, simulate, and calibrate its operation with Peligre minimum criteria elaborated in chapter 2.

3.2 Peligre and Dos Bocas Average Monthly Flow

The hydro-geology of the Dos Bocas watershed is different than the hydro-geology of Peligre. Therefore, adjustment of the river flow for Dos Bocas by area ratio will overestimate the flow. A water balance procedure using rainfall data from 1911 to 2011, and watershed parameters

specific to the water balance analysis will be used to determine the watershed average monthly flows at Dos Bocas. The results are listed in table 6.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
	m ³ /s											
Peligre historical	24	22	20	33	130	153	98	94	133	154	83	44
Peligre	27	22	22	44	128	153	93	103	150	165	75	37
Dos Bocas	16	18	15	40	130	108	60	98	121	110	50	23

Table 6: Peligre and Dos Bocas Average Monthly Flow by Water Balance

3.3 Peligre and Dos Bocas Operational Calibration and Simulation

The challenge of operating two hydroelectric facilities in cascade is that both facilities must be calibrated for the optimum energy production. For Dos Bocas a total of 75 simulations were performed by varying the minimum flow release from its reservoir, and the unit turbine design flow. The results of these simulations are listed in Appendix B. The flow output from the Dos Bocas reservoir was applied to the Peligre reservoir and its operations compared to the operational constraints previously elaborated. The optimum Dos Bocas project data from the 75 simulations are listed in table 7.

ITEMS		
Dam Crest	221.00	m
Maximum Water Level	219.00	m
Minimum Water Level	207.00	m
Power House	177.00	m
Gross Head	42.00	m
Maximum Flow	149.75	m ³ /s
Minimum Flow	18.70	m ³ /s
Design Flow	150.00	m ³ /s
Maximum Power	54.30	Mw
Minimum Power	8.98	Mw
Average Power	25.71	Mw
Annual Energy Output	225,216,756	Mwh
Reservoir Area	54.00	km ²
Reservoir Volume	0.94	km ³

Table 7: Dos Bocas Project Data Alternate Proposal

A partial result from the cascading simulations of Peligre and Dos Bocas are illustrated in figure 5 and 6 for a Dos Bocas reservoir minimum outflow of 30 m³/s that will guarantee a Peligre reservoir minimum outflow of 41 m³/s.

The alternate Dos Bocas proposal will be located at the confluence of the Artibonite River with the Macassia River. The reservoir will have an area of 54.00 km², of which 9.8 km² will be in the Dominican Republic, and 44.2 km² will be in the Republic of Haiti. The Dos Bocas hydroelectric facility will have four turbines of the Francis type each capable of generating 13,625 kw for a total plant capacity of 54,500 kw. The minimum anticipated minimum power

during the dry season will be 8,982 kw, the maximum power during the wet season will be 54,296 kw, and the yearly average will be 25,710 kw. The proposed dam will be a roller compacted concrete-earth fill dam with a crest sets at elevation 221.00 m, lower than elevation 226.00 m of the city of Hinché.

The operation of Dos Bocas and Peligre will need to be closely monitored. This report recommends a possible configuration for Dos Bocas. The results from the optimization of these two cascading facilities are listed in table 8 and table 9. These results demonstrate the net positive impact of Dos Bocas on Peligre.

Facility	Energy	Min Power	Avg. Power	Max. Power	Min. Reservoir Elevation	Min. Reservoir Outflow
	Gwh	kw	kw	kw	m	m ³ /s
Dos Bocas	225,216,756	8,982	25,710	54,296	217.57	30.00
Peligre	285,016,684	16,609	32,536	52,344	168.78	41.00
Total	510,233,440	25,591	58,246	106,640		

Table 8: Peligre and Dos Bocas General Results

The results from this table shows that the objectives for Peligre have been achieved. The energy production with the 2016 reservoir volume is comparable to either the 1956, or the 1979 reservoir volume. The minimum reservoir elevation during the dry season is also higher, meaning that the downstream migration of the sediments will be reduced. The minimum flow release of 41.00 m³/s is also maintained.

DOS BOCAS DESIGN FLOW EFFECT TO "PELIGRE + DOS BOCAS" AVERAGE POWER

Figure 5: *Dos Bocas Optimum Design Flow Effect on "Dos Bocas + Peligre" Capacity*

DOS BOCAS MINIMUM FLOW RELEASE EFFECT TO "PELIGRE + DOS BOCAS" AVERAGE POWER

Figure 6: *Dos Bocas Optimum Minimum Flow Effect on "Dos Bocas + Peligre" Capacity*

Facility	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
	kw	kw	kw									
Dos Bocas	9325	9207	9102	9263	24049	45034	32989	26898	36750	53029	36721	15750
Peligre	17567	17348	17092	16767	39320	51267	42903	35177	45766	52328	45576	18855
Total	26892	26555	26194	26030	63369	96301	75892	62075	82516	105357	82297	34605

Table 9: Peligre and Dos Bocas Average Monthly Power Capacity Working in Cascade

4 Conclusion

The Dos Bocas bi-national project will greatly benefit the Republic of Haiti, and the Dominican Republic. This project located at the confluence of the Artibonite River with the Macassia River will create a vast reservoir that will serve a dual purpose of flow regulation and the production of electrical energy. The project will consist of four Francis turbines having a capacity of 13,625 kw for a total plant capacity of 54,500 kw. The reservoir will cover an area of 54.00 km², of which 44.20 km² are in the Republic of Haiti, and 9.80 km² in the Dominican Republic. Currently INDRHI is proposing a 90 Mw facility, but there are elevation constraints, flow constraints, and downstream effects to Peligre that justify a different approach. The city of Hinche limits the crest elevation of the Dos Bocas dam to less than 226.00 m, while the crest of Peligre dam limits the turbine setting of the Dos Bocas dam to above 175.00 m.

To converge toward an optimum proposal for Dos Bocas, a total of 75 simulations of Dos Bocas and Peligre working in cascade have been performed. These analyses justify the alternate proposal for this study.

This report will serve as a starting point for discussions between the Republic of Haiti, and the Dominican Republic. This project will be beneficial to both countries, and will greatly benefit their economy.

Discussion items for both countries in reference to the alternate Dos Bocas project could be:

1. Sharing of the energy produced by Dos Bocas on a 50% split.
2. Interconnection of the country's electrical grids.
3. Allotment of a portion of the Dos Bocas storage volume during the rainy season to the Dominican Republic, but not to be detrimental to the operation of Peligre.
4. Creation of an independent bi-lateral management entity that will oversees the operations of both Peligre and Dos Bocas.
5. Funds generated by the sale of energy shall be used to finance community based renewable energy projects in both countries.
6. Put in place weather monitoring stations, and river gauging stations throughout the Peligre and Dos Bocas watersheds.
7. Put in place a program of watershed management geared toward reducing erosion in the watershed.
8. Transform the agriculture in the watershed by implementing new irrigation methods for water conservation.

The implementation and success of this project depends on the bi-national cooperation of both the Republic of Haiti, and the Dominican Republic.

5 References

- (CIAT) Comite Inter-Ministeriel Amenagement du Territoire. (n.d.). *Barrages de l'Artibonite Objectifs et Strategies Territoriales pour la Reconstruction*. Port-au-Prince, Haiti.
- (INDRHI), Instituto National de Recursos Hidraulico. (March 2013). *Proyecto de Manejo de la Cuenca Hidrografica del Artibonito*. Santo Domingo, Republica Dominicana.
- Artelia. (May, 2014). *PMDN – Evaluation Integree Des Alternatives de Developpement du Bassin Versant de L' Artibonite, Focalisee sur les Usages Multiples de l' Eau*.
- Coyne et Bellier, L. S. (March, 1998). *Etude de Surelevation du Barrage de Peligre*. Montreal, Quebec.
- Jean-Pierre Tournier, M. F. (February 1982). *Cas historique de sédimentation du barrage Péligre, Haïti*. Montreal, Quebec.
- Mitchell, F. (March 2021). *Haiti GIS-Based Hydropower Potential Mapping Atlas*. Miami, Florida.
- Morris, G. L. (2008). *Sedimentation Study of Peligre Reservoir, Haiti*. San Juan, Puerto Rico.
- Volker Brost, T. T. (n.d.). *Rehabilitation of Péligre Hydro Plant in Haiti*. Port-au-Prince, Haiti.
- Worldwatch Institute. (2014). *Haiti Sustainable Energy Roadmap - Harnessing Domestic Energy Resources to Build a Reliable, Affordable, and Climate-Compatible Electricity System*. Washington.

Appendix A

Peligre Capacity Baseline Evaluation

Baseline Evaluation using 1956 reservoir storage data

ENERGY PRODUCTION SIMULATION USING DAY TO DAY RIVER FLOW FOR PELIGRE USING 1956 RESERVOIR VOLUME

Turbine Design Flow:	41.000	m ³ /s	Minimum Reservoir Elevation	153.00	m	Storage Volume	0.00	m ³				
Turbine Design Elevation:	118.60	m	Maximum Reservoir Elevation	172.00	m	Storage Volume	464816105.71	m ³				
Generator Efficiency:	0.98											
Powerline Efficiency:	0.99		Turbine 1 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 1	40.999	m ³ /s				
Penstock Diameter:	3800	mm	Turbine 2 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 2	26.695	m ³ /s				
Penstock Length:	90	m	Turbine 3 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 3	26.695	m ³ /s				
Penstock Manning	0.015		Turbine 1 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	153.00	m							
Minimum Power	11400	KW	Turbine 2 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m							
Low Flow Reduction Factor:	1.00		Turbine 3 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m							
BEGIN DATE	1/1/2025											
END DATE	12/30/2025	365	Days	8760	Hours			Tariff 0.15 \$/KWH				
Energy Turbine 1	148,913,436	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 1	8760	Hours	Power Turbine 1	13838	16999	17692	KW	Income for Turbine 1	\$ 22,337,015.46
Energy Turbine 2	81,367,142	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 2	4959	Hours	Power Turbine 2	10828	16408	17588	KW	Income for Turbine 2	\$ 12,205,071.29
Energy Turbine 3	54,093,241	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 3	3402	Hours	Power Turbine 3	10839	15900	17457	KW	Income for Turbine 3	\$ 8,113,986.12
TOTAL ENERGY	284,373,819	KWH				Total	16093	32463	52337	KW	Total Income	\$ 42,656,072.87

PELIGRE YEARLY POWER DURATION CURVE (1956 RESERVOIR)

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. TURBINES OUTFLOW

RESERVOIR LEVEL VARIATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW-OUTFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR LEVEL

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. RESERVOIR OUTFLOW

PELIGRE AVERAGE MONTHLY POWER (1956 RESERVOIR)

January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW
17577	17238	16749	16253	27593	46475	45587	35172	49665	52320	45569	18853

Baseline Evaluation using 1979 reservoir storage data

ENERGY PRODUCTION SIMULATION USING DAY TO DAY RIVER FLOW FOR PELIGRE USING 1979 RESERVOIR VOLUME

Turbine Design Flow:	41.000	m ³ /s	Minimum Reservoir Elevation	153.00	m	Storage Volume	0.00	m ³				
Turbine Design Elevation:	118.60	m	Maximum Reservoir Elevation	172.00	m	Storage Volume	382157416.01	m ³				
Generator Efficiency:	0.98											
Powerline Efficiency:	0.99		Turbine 1 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 1	40.999	m ³ /s				
Penstock Diameter:	3800	mm	Turbine 2 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 2	26.695	m ³ /s				
Penstock Length:	90	m	Turbine 3 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 3	26.695	m ³ /s				
Penstock Manning	0.015		Turbine 1 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	153.00	m							
Minimum Power	11400	KW	Turbine 2 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m							
Low Flow Reduction Factor:	1.00		Turbine 3 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m							
BEGIN DATE	1/1/2025											
END DATE	12/30/2025	365	Days	8760	Hours			Tariff 0.15 \$/KWH				
Energy Turbine 1	149,099,068	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 1	8760	Hours	Power Turbine 1	13871	17020	17690	KW	Income for Turbine 1	\$ 22,364,860.14
Energy Turbine 2	81,518,704	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 2	4959	Hours	Power Turbine 2	10851	16439	17586	KW	Income for Turbine 2	\$ 12,227,805.54
Energy Turbine 3	54,248,988	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 3	3402	Hours	Power Turbine 3	10864	15946	17455	KW	Income for Turbine 3	\$ 8,137,348.19
TOTAL ENERGY	284,866,759	KWH				Total	16118	32519	52330	KW	Total Income	\$ 42,730,013.86

PELIGRE YEARLY POWER DURATION CURVE (1979 RESERVOIR)

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. TURBINES OUTFLOW

RESERVOIR LEVEL VARIATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW-OUTFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR LEVEL

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. RESERVOIR OUTFLOW

PELIGRE AVERAGE MONTHLY POWER (1979 RESERVOIR)

January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW
17591	17282	16801	16287	27659	47010	45553	35167	49658	52314	45563	18851

Baseline Evaluation using 2016 reservoir storage data

ENERGY PRODUCTION SIMULATION USING DAY TO DAY RIVER FLOW FOR PELIGRE USING 2016 RESERVOIR VOLUME

Turbine Design Flow:	41.000	m ³ /s	Minimum Reservoir Elevation	153.00	m	Storage Volume	0.00	m ³				
Turbine Design Elevation:	118.60	m	Maximum Reservoir Elevation	172.00	m	Storage Volume	210604933.86	m ³				
Generator Efficiency:	0.98											
Powerline Efficiency:	0.99		Turbine 1 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 1	40.999	m ³ /s				
Penstock Diameter:	3800	mm	Turbine 2 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 2	26.695	m ³ /s				
Penstock Length:	90	m	Turbine 3 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 3	26.695	m ³ /s				
Penstock Manning	0.015		Turbine 1 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	153.00	m							
Minimum Power	11400	KW	Turbine 2 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m							
Low Flow Reduction Factor:	1.00		Turbine 3 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m							
BEGIN DATE	1/1/2025											
END DATE	12/30/2025	365	Days	8760	Hours			Tariff 0.15 \$/KWH				
Energy Turbine 1	146,008,244	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 1	8760	Hours	Power Turbine 1	12564	16668	17695	KW	Income for Turbine 1	\$ 21,901,236.64
Energy Turbine 2	80,541,909	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 2	4959	Hours	Power Turbine 2	9750	16242	17591	KW	Income for Turbine 2	\$ 12,081,286.39
Energy Turbine 3	53,409,577	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 3	3402	Hours	Power Turbine 3	9878	15699	17459	KW	Income for Turbine 3	\$ 8,011,436.56
TOTAL ENERGY	279,959,731	KWH				Total	14105	31959	52344	KW	Total Income	\$ 41,993,959.58

PELIGRE YEARLY POWER DURATION CURVE (2016 RESERVOIR)

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. TURBINES OUTFLOW

RESERVOIR LEVEL VARIATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW-OUTFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR LEVEL

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. RESERVOIR OUTFLOW

PELIGRE AVERAGE MONTHLY POWER (2016 RESERVOIR)

January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW
17542	17115	16192	14662	25239	44931	45724	35177	49672	52328	45576	18855

Peligre reservoir minimum outflow required for maximum energy output

ENERGY PRODUCTION SIMULATION USING DAY TO DAY RIVER FLOW FOR PELIGRE USING 2016 RESERVOIR VOLUME AND RESERVOIR MANAGEMENT

Turbine Design Flow:	41.000	m ³ /s	Minimum Reservoir Elevation	153.00	m	Storage Volume	0.00	m ³				
Turbine Design Elevation:	118.60	m	Maximum Reservoir Elevation	172.00	m	Storage Volume	210604933.86	m ³				
Generator Efficiency:	0.98											
Powerline Efficiency:	0.99		Turbine 1 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 1	12.807	m ³ /s				
Penstock Diameter:	3800	mm	Turbine 2 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 2	12.807	m ³ /s				
Penstock Length:	90	m	Turbine 3 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 3	12.807	m ³ /s				
Penstock Manning	0.015		Turbine 1 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	172.00	m							
Minimum Power	4000	KW	Turbine 2 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	172.00	m							
Low Flow Reduction Factor:	1.00		Turbine 3 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	172.00	m							
BEGIN DATE	1/1/2025											
END DATE	12/30/2025	365	Days	8760	Hours			Tariff 0.15 \$/KWH				
Energy Turbine 1	135,806,493	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 1	8760	Hours	Power Turbine 1	8890	15503	17693	KW	Income for Turbine 1	\$ 20,370,973.95
Energy Turbine 2	88,473,817	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 2	5265	Hours	Power Turbine 2	3994	16804	17592	KW	Income for Turbine 2	\$ 13,271,072.54
Energy Turbine 3	60,101,521	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 3	3925	Hours	Power Turbine 3	3976	15312	17460	KW	Income for Turbine 3	\$ 9,015,228.21
TOTAL ENERGY	284,381,831	KWH				Total	8890	32464	52345	KW	Total Income	\$ 42,657,274.70

PELIGRE YEARLY POWER DURATION CURVE (2016 RESERVOIR)

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. TURBINES OUTFLOW

RESERVOIR LEVEL VARIATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW-OUTFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR LEVEL

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. RESERVOIR OUTFLOW

PELIGRE AVERAGE MONTHLY POWER (2016 RESERVOIR) - OPTIMIZED FOR MAXIMUM ENERGY PRODUCTION

January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW
14311	10244	9036	12243	35351	52328	47982	36890	50816	52328	46619	20656

Appendix B

Dos Bocas Capacity Optimization – Results of Simulation

MINIMUM OUTFLOW DOS BOCAS TO PELIGRE	DOS BOCAS			PELIGRE			TOTAL AVERAGE POWER
	TURBINES UNIT FLOW (M ³ /S)	AVERAGE POWER (KW)	LOWEST RESERVOIR LEVEL (M)	TURBINES UNIT FLOW (M ³ /S)	AVERAGE POWER (KW)	LOWEST RESERVOIR LEVEL (M)	
20.00	40.00	24928	218.93	41.00	31103	161.70	56031
25.00	40.00	25024	218.38	41.00	31359	165.28	56383
30.00	40.00	25105	217.57	41.00	31615	168.76	56720
35.00	40.00	24983	216.61	41.00	31470	171.00	56453
38.18	40.00	24289	215.94	41.00	30799	171.99	55088
40.00	40.00	23906	215.56	41.00	30379	172.00	54285
20.00	41.00	25167	218.93	41.00	31103	161.70	56270
25.00	41.00	25261	218.38	41.00	31355	165.28	56616
30.00	41.00	25333	217.57	41.00	31537	168.76	56870
35.00	41.00	25236	216.61	41.00	31153	171.00	56389
38.18	41.00	24448	215.94	41.00	30480	171.99	54928
40.00	41.00	24065	215.54	41.00	30123	172.00	54188
41.00	41.00	23885	215.33	41.00	29954	172.00	53839
20.00	42.00	25376	218.93	41.00	31103	161.70	56479
25.00	42.00	25465	218.37	41.00	31271	165.28	56736
30.00	42.00	25531	217.57	41.00	31347	168.76	56878
35.00	42.00	25240	216.61	41.00	30902	171.01	56142
38.18	42.00	24590	215.94	41.00	30193	171.99	54783
40.00	42.00	24219	215.54	41.00	29920	172.00	54139
41.00	42.00	24020	215.31	41.00	29736	172.00	53756
42.00	42.00	23840	215.11	41.00	29566	172.00	53406
20.00	43.00	25549	218.93	41.00	31103	161.70	56652
25.00	43.00	25636	218.37	41.00	31200	165.28	56836
30.00	43.00	25695	217.57	41.00	31232	168.76	56927
35.00	43.00	25243	216.61	41.00	30584	171.02	55827
38.18	43.00	24705	215.94	41.00	29993	172.00	54698
40.00	43.00	24325	215.54	41.00	29768	172.00	54093
41.00	43.00	24124	215.31	41.00	29583	172.00	53707
42.00	43.00	23909	215.09	41.00	29396	172.00	53305
43.00	43.00	23677	214.88	41.00	29285	172.00	52962
20.00	44.00	25680	218.93	41.00	31144	161.93	56824
25.00	44.00	25765	218.37	41.00	31112	165.28	56877
30.00	44.00	25823	217.57	41.00	31040	168.76	56863
35.00	44.00	25261	216.61	41.00	30299	171.05	55560
38.18	44.00	24768	215.94	41.00	29843	171.93	54611

40.00	44.00	24406	215.54	41.00	29573	172.00	53979
41.00	44.00	24143	215.31	41.00	29489	172.00	53632
42.00	44.00	23846	215.09	41.00	29320	172.00	53166
43.00	44.00	23548	214.86	41.00	29211	172.00	52759
44.00	44.00	23411	214.64	41.00	29095	172.00	52506
20.00	45.00	25744	218.93	41.00	31104	161.70	56848
25.00	45.00	25860	218.37	41.00	31019	165.28	56879
30.00	45.00	25913	217.57	41.00	30864	168.76	56777
35.00	45.00	25260	216.61	41.00	30157	171.03	55417
38.18	45.00	24770	215.94	41.00	29718	172.00	54488
40.00	45.00	24321	215.54	41.00	29468	172.00	53789
41.00	45.00	24049	215.31	41.00	29335	172.00	53384
42.00	45.00	23932	215.09	41.00	29137	172.00	53069
43.00	45.00	27788	214.86	41.00	29003	172.00	56791
44.00	45.00	23636	214.62	41.00	28869	172.00	52505
45.00	45.00	23498	214.41	41.00	28734	172.00	52232
20.00	46.00	25838	218.93	41.00	31104	161.70	56942
25.00	46.00	25922	218.37	41.00	30950	165.28	56872
30.00	46.00	25973	217.57	41.00	30691	168.76	56664
35.00	46.00	25221	216.61	41.00	30026	171.03	55247
38.18	46.00	24582	215.94	41.00	29650	172.00	54232
40.00	46.00	24346	215.54	41.00	29331	172.00	53677
41.00	46.00	24251	215.31	41.00	29131	172.00	53382
42.00	46.00	24145	215.09	41.00	28927	172.00	53072
30.00	47.00	25819	217.57	41.00	30522	168.76	56341
30.00	48.00	25661	217.57	41.00	30397	168.76	56058
30.00	49.00	25525	217.57	41.00	30267	168.76	55792
30.00	50.00	25297	217.57	41.00	30334	168.76	55631
30.00	51.00	25190	217.57	41.00	30243	168.76	55433
30.00	52.00	25214	217.57	41.00	30949	168.76	56163
30.00	53.00	25225	217.57	41.00	31509	168.76	56734
30.00	54.00	25224	217.57	41.00	31485	168.76	56709
30.00	55.00	25218	217.57	41.00	31327	168.76	56545
30.00	60.00	24914	217.57	41.00	30323	168.76	55237
30.00	65.00	25393	217.57	41.00	29495	168.76	54888
30.00	70.00	25649	217.57	41.00	30891	168.76	56540
30.00	75.00	25709	217.57	41.00	31485	168.76	57194
30.00	80.00	25579	217.57	41.00	31546	168.76	57125
30.00	85.00	25386	217.57	41.00	31063	168.76	56449
30.00	90.00	25188	217.57	41.00	30650	168.76	55838

Appendix C

Peligre and Dos Bocas Cascade Operation

Dos Bocas Simulation Results for Optimum Cascade Operation

DOS BOCAS - LAKE AREA AND VOLUME

ENERGY PRODUCTION SIMULATION USING DAY TO DAY RIVER FLOW WITH RESERVOIR MANAGEMENT FOR DOS BOCAS

Turbine Design Flow (2):	75.000	m ³ /s	Minimum Reservoir Elevation	200.00	m	Storage Volume	0.00	m ³				
Turbine Design Elevation:	174.00	m	Maximum Reservoir Elevation	219.00	m	Storage Volume	937016195.90	m ³				
Generator Efficiency:	0.98											
Powerline Efficiency:	0.99		Turbine 1+2 "on" Elevation	200.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 1+2	30.031	m ³ /s				
Penstock Diameter:	5700	mm	Turbine 3+4 "on" Elevation	200.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 3+4	30.031	m ³ /s				
Penstock Length:	227	m	Turbine 5+6 "on" Elevation	219.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 5+6	22.824	m ³ /s				
Penstock Manning	0.015		Turbine 1+2 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	200.00	m							
Minimum Turbine Flow:	5360	KW	Turbine 3+4 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	200.00	m							
Low Flow Reduction Factor:	1.00		Turbine 5+6 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	215.00	m							
BEGIN DATE	1/1/2025											
END DATE	12/30/2025	365	Days	8760	Hours							
						Minimum >0	Average	Maximum				
Energy Turbine 1+2	173,455,285	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 1+2	8760	Hours	8982	19801	27287	KW	Income for Turbine 1+2	\$ 26,018,292.80	
Energy Turbine 3+4	51,761,471	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 3+4	2681	Hours	9034	19307	27140	KW	Income for Turbine 3+4	\$ 7,764,220.64	
Energy Turbine 5+6	-	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 5+6	0	Hours	0	0	0	KW	Income for Turbine 5+6	\$ -	
TOTAL ENERGY	225,216,756	KWH				Total	8982	25710	54296	KW	Total Income	\$ 33,782,513.44
										Tariff	0.15 \$/KWH	

DOS BOCAS YEARLY POWER DURATION CURVE

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. TURBINES OUTFLOW

RESERVOIR LEVEL VARIATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW-OUTFLOW

DOS BOCAS POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW

DOS BOCAS POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR LEVEL

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. RESERVOIR OUTFLOW

DOS BOCAS AVERAGE MONTHLY POWER

January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW
9325	9207	9102	9263	24049	45034	32989	26898	36570	53029	36721	15750

Peligre Simulation Results for Optimum Cascade Operation

PELIGRE - LAKE SURFACE AREA AND STORAGE

ENERGY PRODUCTION SIMULATION USING DAY TO DAY RIVER FLOW FOR PELIGRE USING 2016 RESERVOIR VOLUME, RESERVOIR MANAGEMENT, AND DOS BOCAS UPSTREAM

Turbine Design Flow:	41.000	m³/s	Minimum Reservoir Elevation	153.00	m	Storage Volume	0.00	m³	
Turbine Design Elevation:	118.60	m	Maximum Reservoir Elevation	172.00	m	Storage Volume	210604933.86	m³	
Generator Efficiency:	0.98								
Powerline Efficiency:	0.99		Turbine 1 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 1	40.999	m³/s	
Penstock Diameter:	3800	mm	Turbine 2 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 2	26.695	m³/s	
Penstock Length:	90	m	Turbine 3 "on" Elevation	153.00	m	Low Power Flow Turbine 3	26.695	m³/s	
Penstock Manning	0.015		Turbine 1 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	153.00	m				
Minimum Power	11400	KW	Turbine 2 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m				
Low Flow Reduction Factor:	1.00		Turbine 3 Low Power Flow Start Elevation	170.00	m				
BEGIN DATE	1/1/2025								
END DATE	12/30/2025	365	Days	8760	Hours			Tariff 0.15 \$/KWH	
Energy Turbine 1	150,898,781	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 1	8760	Hours	Power Turbine 1			
Energy Turbine 2	83,298,386	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 2	4959	Hours	Power Turbine 2			
Energy Turbine 3	50,819,518	KWH	Hours of Operations Turbine 3	3055	Hours	Power Turbine 3			
TOTAL ENERGY	285,016,684	KWH				Total			
						Minimum > 0	Average	Maximum	
						14379	17226	17695	KW
						11231	16797	17591	KW
						11262	16635	17459	KW
						16609	32536	52344	KW
									Income for Turbine 1 \$ 22,634,817.08
									Income for Turbine 2 \$ 12,494,757.84
									Income for Turbine 3 \$ 7,622,927.74
									Total Income \$ 42,752,502.66

PELIGRE YEARLY POWER DURATION CURVE (2016 RESERVOIR AND DOS BOCAS UPSTREAM)

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. TURBINES OUTFLOW

RESERVOIR LEVEL VARIATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW-OUTFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR INFLOW

PELIGRE POWER DURATION SIMULATION vs. RESERVOIR LEVEL

RESERVOIR INFLOW vs. RESERVOIR OUTFLOW

PELIGRE AVERAGE MONTHLY POWER (2016 RESERVOIR AND DOS BOCAS UPSTREAM)

January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW	KW
17567	17348	17092	16767	29320	51267	42903	35177	45766	52328	45576	18855

Appendix D

Peligre and Dos Bocas Exhibits

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
26.9900	21.7800	22.4000	44.2100	128.3000	153.4500	92.7500	103.4400	150.1600	165.3900	75.0700	36.5200

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
WATERSHED AREA	6,700.75	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	71.81	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
SOIL CAPACITY	269.55	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.34	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.21	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	23.03	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Watershed
 - Selected Site Dam
 - Selected Site Reservoir
 - Capital
 - Chef Lieu
 - Place
 - Roads
 - Rivers
 - Lakes
 - Departements

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
17,567	17,347	17,090	16,763	26,944	51,631	42,309	35,177	44,896	52,328	41,932	17,679

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Gravity
DAM HEIGHT	53.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	31.47	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	19.00	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	172.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	118.60	(m)
GROSS HEAD	53.40	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	3.80	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	90.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	3.00	Francis
DESIGN FLOW	123.00	(cubic meter per second)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
52328	31845	16603	278965646

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Station
 - Selected Site Reservoir

PELIGRE DAM

SECTION THROUGH POWER STATION

LOCATION KEY MAP

MONTHLY MODELED AVERAGE FLOW VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
15.9062	17.7265	15.2975	39.9504	129.7259	107.8637	60.4091	97.9871	121.4599	110.4081	49.6354	23.3441

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS			LEGEND	
PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION	Symbol	Description
WATERSHED AREA	5,896.80	(Sq. km)	[Orange outline]	Selected Site Watershed
SCS-CN	71.48	(SCS - Average Curve Number)	[Circle]	Place
SOIL CAPACITY	267.72	(mm)	[Red line]	Roads
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)	[Blue outline]	Selected Site Reservoir
GWF	0.34	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)	[Blue outline]	Lakes
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)	[Blue outline]	Departements
RFLK	0.22	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)	[Red star]	Capital
BFLK	17.61	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)	[Red star]	Chef Lieu

LOCATION KEY MAP

AVERAGE MONTHLY MODELED POWER POTENTIAL VALUES (UNIT: KW)

JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
9,313	9,193	9,088	9,252	24,053	45,040	33,004	26,900	36,584	53,029	36,721	15,750

SITE DESIGN PARAMETERS

SITE ITEMS	VALUES	UNITS/DESCRIPTION
DAM TYPE	1.00	Earth Fill
DAM HEIGHT	47.00	(m)
RESERVOIR AVERAGE AREA	54.00	(Sq. km)
RESERVOIR STORAGE HEIGHT	19.00	(m)
WATER ELEVATION	219.00	(m)
POWER HOUSE ELEVATION	174.00	(m)
GROSS HEAD	45.00	(m)
PENSTOCK DIAMETER	5.79	(m)
PENSTOCK LENGTH	227.00	(m)
CANAL WIDTH	0.00	(m)
CANAL LENGTH	0.00	(m)
NUMBER OF TURBINES	4.00	Francis
DESIGN FLOW	150.00	(cubic meter per second)

SITE CAPACITY (UNITS: KW, KWH)

MAX. POWER	AVG. POWER	MIN. POWER	ANNUAL ENERGY
54296	25709	8969	225209464

- LEGEND**
- Selected Site Station
 - Selected Site Reservoir

DOS BOCAS PROPOSED DAM

SECTION THROUGH POWER STATION

